

MEASURING TOURISTS' ATTITUDE AND ATTEMPTS TOWARDS GREEN PRACTICES IN TOURISM: A CASE OF COX'S BAZAR

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Abstract

With the diverse positive contributions of the tourism today, its negative impact on the environment is a matter of worry. Especially, pollution of the environment by the tourism activities has made concern to the stakeholders which leads to the green tourism practices. Green tourism practices focus on trying to minimize the negative impact on the environment through applying the various tools and techniques. The basic objective of the study is to examine the attitude of the tourists and their real actions toward green practices. This research is exploratory in nature. The structured questionnaire is used to collect the required data of this study. A mathematical model is used to analyze the collected data. The study reveals that in the context of genuine activities by the tourists, some green practices are found among them and the maximum actions toward green tourism practices are frustrating. Several recommendations for the tourists are proposed that may be followed by them for the betterment of the future environment.

Keywords: Tourism, Green Tourism Practice, Recycling.

Introduction

Tourism is the most important international economic force in the 21st century. It is considered as a growing business all over the world. The UNCTAD (2007) identifies tourism as the largest and fastest rising industry in the world. World Tourism Organization (WTO) (2021) states that tourism has grown to be one of the largest trade sectors in the world, with exports of goods and services to the industry totaling USD 11.7 trillion in 2019, or 28% of all global service trade and 7% of all exports of goods and services. In its annual report, the World Travel and Tourism

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Council (WTTC) (2020) affirms that in 2019, the tourism industry supported 330 million jobs, or 10% of all jobs worldwide, and contributed 10% of global GDP. One in four of all net new jobs created worldwide over the previous five years were in the travel and tourism sector. It is forecasted to rise by 6.5% per annum to 4.7% of GDP by 2024. As stated by Tuhin and Mojumdar (2011), nowadays tourism is the most beneficial and modern business throughout the world. Like other developing countries, tourism has turned out to be a significant sector for economic escalation in Bangladesh (Islam, 2009). Mondal & Haque (2018) found that the country has immense opportunities to create jobs for youths, promote local culture, encourage local entrepreneurship, and above all increase economic benefits through developing sustainable tourism, which can also contribute to achieving the targets of Sustainable Development Goals by 2030. Tourism is one of the most profitable in Bangladesh (Elena et al., 2012). Sultana (2016) stated that tourism is a growing industry in

Bangladesh. The tourism industry of Bangladesh is gaining international attention. Tourism's contribution to poverty alleviation has been recognized by the National Tourism Policy 1992 (Bangladesh Tourism Vision 2020, 2006). But tourism industry is criticized by the environmental-conscious people. It is because that the tourism sector is one of the main sources of environmental damage in the form of atmospheric pollution, soil erosion and the loss of natural habitat (Mikayilov et al., 2019). Therefore, the tourism sector contributes to environmental damage. On the other side, there is a growing awareness of environmental deterioration. The rising awareness of the impact of daily human actions on the environment has led to the recognition that with tourism industry all individuals and businesses should be engaged in reducing environmental pollution. According to Sloan, Legrand, and Chen (2009), stockholders, employees and customers have increasing expectations of the tourism and hospitality industry to be economically, socially, and environmentally responsible. It is important to redecorate the general perspective and actions about environmental matters and tourism. If not, no safety tourism possibility in the future will remain. Tourists are becoming demanding for green tourism. Increase consciousness of the people leads the tourism business to be caring for the environment. As a result, green practices in tourism have evolved. The deepest thoughts are: whether tourists have the positive attitudes toward green practices? Which issues among green practices are important to them? What are their actual practices toward green matters in tourism? To find the answer to these questions attitude of the tourists is evaluated and searched for their real activities of green practices.

Justification of the Study

Bangladesh is to compete with the global rivals with tourism products and services. Lenzen et al. (2018) found that tourism accounts for 8% of greenhouse gas emissions. Now conscious individuals are worried about the negative effect of tourism on the environment. Han & Kim (2010) opine that the green concept is attracting more and more attention from both companies

and consumers and has acquired greater relevance in recent years. Consumers are becoming more and more concerned with the issues caused by climate change (Juvan & Dolnicar, 2017; Rahman et al., 2012). Their views stress the tourism business to rethink of influence of tourism on the environment which gives birth to new concept „Green Tourism Practices”. As per Franco, Grewal, Hoang & Lee (2014), it is evident that there is a good effect when accommodations allocate a portion of money to green marketing. It supports the notion that if society has a vested interest in environmental issues, it can lead many businesses, including hotels to change their practices. Green practices minimize the negative environmental impact of tourism. The most important side effect of going green is to create a more sustainable environment (Fyall et al., 2009). In this research, the choice of issue is influenced by practical and scientific concern. This study can provide some recommendations to make and take the opportunity of green tourism practices in Bangladesh. The defining problem of this study is a timely one and widespread from the sense of areas of consequence. Therefore, the study is accurately justified.

Statement of the Research Problem

Air emissions, noise, solid waste and littering, sewage, oil, and chemical discharges, as well as architectural and visual pollution, are all potential effects of tourism (Camarda, D., & Grassini, L., 2003). According to Azam, Alam, & Hafeez (2018); Hassan, Kennell, & Chaperon (2020); Sun, Yesilada, Andlib, & Ajaz.(2021) since tourism growth and environmental sustainability are thought to be interrelated concepts, a rise in tourism development and visitor numbers will directly affect the level of sustainable and green tourism. Azam et al. (2018) and Hoang, Van Rompaey, Meyfroidt et al. (2020) clarify that negative consequences of tourism development result in many problems for the tourists and the indigenous people in the foreseeable future. Prior research revealed that air pollution, energy use, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and arrival of tourists as a result of international tourism and tourism-led growth spurt contribute to climate change (Aslan et al., 2012). From the above discussion it is clear that today green practices by the tourists are immensely important. To compete with the global competitor tourism industry must take the green factors in considerations with importance. For the business people, understanding and analyzing the attitudes of travelers toward green tourism practices is a matter of concentration at this moment. Hence, the pertinent questions of this research are: Do travelers support green practices in tourism? Are they involved in green practices in their real life? Appropriate answers of these questions lie on analyzing the attitudes of tourists and current activities of them toward green practices in tourism.

Objectives of the Study

The prime objectives of this study are to gauge tourist attitudes and investigate their use of environmentally friendly practices. Specific objectives are to -

- Measure the attitudes of the tourists toward green practices in tourism: and
- Assess the actual activities toward green practices in tourism by the tourists.

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no relationship between Green Practices and Personal Efforts in the time of tour by the tourists.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a relationship between Green Practices and Personal Efforts in the time of tour by the tourists.

Literature Review

Amin (2007) identifies tourism as one of the largest industries which is contributing over ten percent (10%) to global GDP. Economically, this industry creates jobs and contributes to a country's GDP bringing in capital investment and exports. According to Rahman (2007), tourism industry of Bangladesh has vast potentials from the sense of foreign exchange earner and provider of job opportunities. It has the resulting multiplier effect on the country's economy all together. However, it is criticized that this industry now has a significant negative impact on the climate and weather. Therefore, weather and climate have brought significance for tourist decision-making and the travel experience ... Both at home and destinations climate is a most important motivator in tourism. Either consciously or by implicitly climate is considered by tourists during tour planning (Daniel Scott, Colin Michael Hall, Stefan Gossling, 2012). Various national and international reports have shown the negative impact of tourism on the weather and climate. Also, several researchers have studied the harmful effects of tourism on the environment. According to UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism (2008), tourism is considered as an extremely climate-sensitive economic segment for its close relations to the environment and climate. In UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism 2008, it is reported that Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the most significant greenhouse gas accounting for an estimated 60% of the warming. A report of UNWTO-UNEP-WMO (2008) expresses that emissions from tourism activities contribute about 5% of worldwide CO₂ emissions. Additional greenhouse gases as well create important contributions to worldwide temperature. Tourism's contribution to worldwide warming was estimated for the year of 2005. It was found that its contribution was between 5% and 14% to the overall warming caused by human being emissions of greenhouse gases⁴. Kreg (2001) explores the generation of the different types of waste and contamination by the tourists.

Zhang et al. (2016) found from the results of variance decomposition method that the unidirectional causality exists between environmental pollution and tourist arrivals, which is running from tourist arrival to environmental pollution. A study conducted by Sghaier et al. (2019) reveals that tourism activities have enhanced environment pollution in Egypt. Today, both tourism marketers and customers are concerned about environmental degradation and are

⁴ UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme) Manuals on Sustainable Tourism (2008), Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation in the Tourism Sector: Frameworks, Tools and Practices, p. 15

taking steps in a green direction. Being green is not only a slogan and promotional scheme; it has become a lifestyle for individuals and a means to cut cost as well as a viable strategy for operators (Andersson et al., 2013; Hanchar, 2017; Martinho et al., 2018; Tommy, 2013). Through the adoption of green practices by a growing number of hotels the hospitality industry is making changes in the interests of their customers. A few smaller upscale hotels are getting 15-20% of their business coming because of their green attempts (Natz, 2008). Practicing green activities in the field is difficult. According to Manaktola, K., and Jauhari (2007), the difficulty is that consumers are aware of environmental practices and prefer them, but they are not ready to pay more for them. Environmental practices are viewed by some customers as a requirement and essential component of the service provided, as demonstrated by Robinot E. and Giannelloni JL. (2010); as a result, the cost shouldn't be included in hotel rates. Despite this, it is obvious that green tourism can offer different benefits as broad economic, social and environmental benefits for the host countries as well as their communities (Mill & Morrison 2006, World Economic Forum 2009, Klytchnikova & Dorosh 2009). Though not important now, it is probable that decision making related to climate will start to influence tourism markets in the future either for tourists' awareness on their personal carbon foot (Simmons & Becken 2004), or for negative changes at destinations.

One-third to one half of international tourists (weighted toward the USA) surveyed in a CESD and TIES (2005) study said if companies benefit local communities and conservation they were ready to pay more. Study by Schubert et al. (2010) illustrates that there is an unfilled market niche for „green“ restaurants, as customers care about restaurants protecting the environment and would be willing to pay more to offset any additional costs associated with “green” practices. According to Bohdanowicz, P. (2003), a large portion of patrons' support is motivating and encouraging some hotels and restaurants to take action toward greater environmental responsibility.

Review of related literatures express that the researches on tourism and green tourism focus on contributions and status of tourism (Amin & Rahman, 2007; Sghaier et al. 2019), influence of climate change in decision making of tourism (Daniel Scott, Colin Michael Hall, and Stefan Gossling,2012), how tourism is affected by climate change (UNEP Manuals on Sustainable Tourism, 2008 and Natz, 2008), the environment is polluted by how and whom from the tourism industry (Glem Kreg, 2001), and benefits of green practices in tourism (Schubert et. Al 2010; Mill and Morrison, 2006; World Economic Forum 2009; Klytchnikova and Dorosh, 2009 and TIES 2005). Literatures provide the evidence that no research was performed emphasizing the various green practices in tourism. By conducting this study this vital research gap is satisfied.

Research Methodology

The research needs the information about the tourists" attitudes and actions toward green practices in tourism. To define the problem precisely the researcher is in the attempts to discuss

with decision makers and interviewing with industry experts. Also, environmental background of the problem is considered by the researcher.

Population, Sampling Technique and Sample Size

In sampling design, the researcher includes defining population, deciding sampling technique and determination of sample size. The population for the study includes tourists visiting Cox's Bazar. Tourists from the various hotels and restaurants are drawn by using simple random sampling method. A total number of 143 tourists are selected as sample. Following formula (M. Nurul Islam, 2014) is applied to determine the sample size.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sample size } n_0 &= \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2} \\ &= \frac{(1.64)^2 (0.5) (0.5)}{(0.07)^2} \\ &= 138 \text{ (approximately)} \end{aligned}$$

Where, n_0 = desired sample size

z = standard normal deviate

p = assumed proportion in the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic

d = allowable maximum error in estimating population proportion

Data Collection: Tools, Techniques and Quality Check

Data are collected through the field survey. Surveys are completed by pre-set questionnaire which contains structured questions. The questionnaire holds scale, dichotomous and open ended questions. The researcher employs personal interview to obtain primary data. For the study the researcher checks the quality of data by repeating questions and probing.

Data Management and Analysis

To draw the findings of the study the researcher has addressed data preparation and exploring, examining, and rearranging data. After collecting the data to identify errors and omissions, make rectifications whenever possible, and certify that minimum data quality standards are achieved, the researcher takes the step of editing. Editing of data is accomplished by in-house editing. Both pre and post-coding (numerical) is applied in the questionnaire. The researcher starts to enter the coded information into a file directly from the questionnaires. In analyzing the real actions of the respondents toward green tourism practices frequency distribution is used. For calculations and statistical test applications, SPSS 21.0 is used. Data are analyzed by employing both the mathematical and graphical model. Malhotra and Dash (2016) assert that graphical models are visible. They are not intended to produce numerical answers; instead, they are used

to isolate variables and to make suggestions about the directions of relationships. Conversely, mathematical models explicitly explain the relationships between variables, typically in the form of equations.

Data Analysis and Findings

Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics

The socioeconomic and demographic information of the respondents has an impact on the study that cannot be ignored. To verify the validity of the study, researchers have gathered the aforementioned data. The following table (Table-1) shows the different socioeconomic and demographic data and also discussed below.

Table 1: The socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Sub-variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	114	80
	Female	29	20
	Total	143	100
Age (Years)	18 – 30	49	35
	31 – 40	53	37
	41 - 50	32	22
	51 - 60	6	4
	61 - 70	3	2
	Total	143	100
Marital Status	Married	104	73
	Single	39	27
	Total	143	100
Level of Education	Primary	16	11
	SSC	16	11
	HSC	23	16
	Graduate	45	32
	Post Graduate	43	30
	Total	143	100
Occupation	Students	15	11
	Self-employed	39	27
	Professional (Teaching, Doctor and Engineering)	27	19
	Manager/Executive	25	17
	Government Officer	27	19
	Unemployed	10	7
	Total	143	100
Monthly Income (taka in thousands)	No income	20	14
	Less than 30	13	9
	30 – 40	31	22
	41 – 50	28	20
	51 - 60	26	18
	More than 60	25	17
	Total	143	100

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2018

Table-1 reveals that among the respondents 80% is male and the remaining 20% of them is female. In the question of age among them 37% respondents are in the range of 31 to 40 years old, 35% are under the range of 18 to 30 years old, and 22% have the age under the range of 41 to 50 years old. It is also clear from the table that 73% of the respondents are married and the rest of them are single. In terms of the level of education, 32% respondents are graduates, 30% are post-graduate, 16% are HSC-pass, 11% are SSC-pass and the remaining 11% are from primary education. In the question of occupation, it is seen from the table that 27% of the respondents are self-employed, 19% are professional, 19% are government officer, 17% are managers/executives, 11% are students and the remaining 7% are unemployed. Monthly income (in thousands taka) is presented in the socio- demographic table. The table demonstrates that 14% of the respondents have no income, 18% have income in the range of 51 to 60 thousand, 17% earn more than 60 thousands taka, 22% have the income of 30 to 40 thousands, 20% of respondents' income is in the range of 41 to 50 thousand and 9% respondents earn less than 30 thousand taka.

Awareness about Green Practices to the Tourists

The researcher assesses whether tourists have the awareness about green practices in tourism. The following chart (Figure-1) shows the result before the question of "Do you know about green practices in tourism?" It is clear from the illustration-1 that among the sample tourists only 26% has the familiarity about green practices in tourism and most of the tourists (74%) have no idea.

Fig. 1.: Displaying the awareness about green practices in tourism

Chance to Exercise Green

The researcher takes the ^{74%}step to know the view of the tourists about if there is any chance to exercise green in the time of tour. The responses are distributed in the following table (Table-2). Table-2 expresses that among the tourists 17% thinks that a tourist can get the option to exercise green and 12% thought is negative on such an issue. Most of the tourists (71%) are confused about whether there is any possibility to exercise green in the time of tour.

Table 2: Distribution of responses regarding the chance of green practices

Responses	Whether there is any chance to exercise green in the time of tour	
	Number	Percent (%)
Yes	24	17
No	18	12
Don't know	101	71
Total	143	100

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2018

Correlation Matrix Analysis

Correlation analysis is the statistical tool we use to describe the degree to which one variable is related to another. The purpose of correlation analysis is to find how strong the relationship is between two variables without making any distinction between dependent and independent variables. One such measure of this relationship is the correlation coefficient (Nurul Islam, 2015). The following table (Table-3) shows the correlation coefficient among Green Practice and the factors involved with personal efforts of tourists.

Table 3: Spearman's rho Correlation Matrix

	Green practice followed by the tourist	Personally solid waste management	Green transportation should be used by the tourists	Procuring green tourism products by the tourist	Green program implementation	Concentration on water conservation program	Having food which are environmental-friendly
Green practice followed by the tourist	1						
Personally solid waste management	.350** (.000)	1					
Green transportation should be used by the tourists	.107 (.203)	.139 (.099)	1				
Procuring green tourism products by the tourist	.084 (.316)	.263** (.001)	.388** (.000)	1			
Green program implementation	.166* (.048)	.236** (.005)	.164* (.050)	.271** (.001)	1		
Concentration on water conservation program	.197* (.018)	.078 (.357)	-.088 (.298)	.016 (.848)	.089 (.289)	1	
Having food which are environmentally-friendly	.318** (.000)	-.016 (.847)	.144 (.086)	.092 (.273)	-.054 (.519)	.102 (.225)	1
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							
(...) parenthesis indicates the p-value.							

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2018

The Table-3 reflects that relationship between green practice and personally solid waste management by the tourists is ($r = 0.350$) is positive and the relationship is statistically highly significant. Also, green practice has the positive and highly significant association with having food which is environmentally-friendly. The table shows that the association of green practice with green program implementation and concentration on the water conservation program are positive and significant at the .05 level. The contribution of using green transportation and procuring green tourism products toward green practices are found positive but not significant. From the analysis, it is vivid that alternative hypothesis can be accepted.

Genuine Role of the Tourists toward Green Practices

Attitude cannot confirm the same behavior which means that attitude and real doings may not be the same. So, the researcher has initiated the step to check the actual practices of tourists to the green issue. The real functions toward the green practices are evaluated by using several variables which are environmental-actions. The tourists are approached whether they used the various green products/services within one year from which decision is made about their real activities toward green practices. The following tables (Tables: 4 – 8) and graphs (Figures: 2 - 3) show the real role of the tourists toward green practices.

Solid waste management program

Personally, each tourist can give the attention for the sake of the environment through solid waste management program. Table-4 reveals genuine actions toward green practices under solid waste management. The table shows that in the case of reusing tote bags, recycled cloths and reusable water bottles tourists had greater positive contributions (80%, 78%, and 57% respectively) to save the environment. It is found from the Table-4 that 92% did not use recycled bathroom soaps and 62% had not any attention to use less toilet items in the hotel within one year. In using recycled paper cups and less linen in the hotel, green practices by the tourists were in the frustrated position. The percent of not-using the first variable was 68 and the later was 61.

Table 4: Responses regarding solid waste management

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Reusable tote bags	115	80	28	20
Reusable water bottles	82	57	61	43
Recycled paper cups	46	32	97	68
Recycled cloths	111	78	32	22
Recycled bathroom soaps	11	8	132	92
Use of less linen in hotel	56	39	87	61
Use of less toilet items in hotel	54	38	89	62

The Table-5 shows the distribution of responses of the sample tourists regarding using public transportation, carpooling, walking instead of driving and renting the hybrid car which are the actual activities toward green practices of them. It is found from the survey that 84% of tourists used public transportation within one year but in case of carpooling among the sample tourists 94% did not go to work or events through carpooling. It is also clear from the table-5 that respondents were not eager (among 143 tourists only 30% rented) to rent the hybrid car. The table-5 demonstrates that 90% of respondents walked instead of driving where possible is a matter of happiness toward green practices.

Table 5: Distribution of responses regarding use of transportation

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Using public transportation	120	84	23	16
Carpool to work or events	9	6	134	94
Walk instead of driving where possible	129	90	14	10
Rented hybrid car	43	30	100	70

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2018

Green procurement

The following table (Table-6) and the figure-2 demonstrate that 49% of the sample tourists procured recycled content products within one year and the remaining did not purchase. It is also shown that 97% did not purchase eco-friendly soaps and in case of buying greening products only 45% of respondents purchased such products.

Table 6: Distribution of responses regarding green procurement

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Buying recycled content products	70	49	73	51
Buying eco-friendly soaps	5	3	138	97
Buying greening products	65	45	78	55

Green programs

The Table-7 and the Figure-3 are the evidences of the responses of the sample tourists regarding using green services and looking for green hotels. It is viewed from the two illustrations that 82% of tourists did not use green services and 89% did not look for green hotel within one year. Only 18% and 11% respondents used green services and searched for green hotel respectively.

Table 7: Responses regarding green programs

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Using green services	26	18	117	82
Looking for green hotels	16	11	127	89

Water conservation

The tourists can contribute to the green practices through participating in the hotel water conservation program. It is vivid from the following table (Table-8) that in water conservation program by the hotel only 41% tourists participated within one year.

Table 8: Responses of the sample tourist regarding water conservation

Item	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Participating in hotel water conservation program	59	41	84	59

Source: Field survey by the researcher, 2018

Conclusion and Recommendations

Tourists have the direct impact on the environment in the time of the tour. Today, over the world awareness about environmental pollution is disseminated to the various stakeholders of the tourism industry. Day by day, tourists are becoming environmentally-friendly which, in the future, will lead to build a comfortable planet. They can contribute a lot to the environment through green practices. Tourists have the chance to exercise green through solid waste management, using transportation, procuring green products, implementing green program, participating water conservation, and buying organic food. Tourists should give concentration to recycled bathroom soaps and recycled paper cups. This effort will confirm to lessening pollution by the chemicals used in soaps and reducing cutting of trees. At last, it will contribute to positive impact to the environment. They also should think about less use of linen and less use of toilet items in the time of staying in the hotel. They should think of renting the hybrid car and also they can consider carpooling to their work or event. These environmental-efforts will help to minimize the pollution. If eco-friendly soaps are offered, visitors should purchase them to follow green lifestyles. Incorporating a green lifestyle into daily life is something that tourists should do. Finding green hotels and utilizing green services are two ways to go green. Hotels and restaurants have water conservation program to save water for the future. Excess use of water will lead the nation to the shortage of water that is a matter of tension for the environment.

Tourists should actively participate in the water conservation program offered by the hotels. Even they should personally heed on such issue.

Limitations and Further Study

The study was rested on more than a few variables which are significant in individual-practice of green in the time of tour. But this initiative cannot check the fullest insights of the issue. It is because that some other aspects beyond the observed variables may influence the attitude and the diverse action of the tourists toward the green practices in tourism. Learning, perception, value, belief, liking, preference etc. can be observable fact for such a form of a research. So, in future, to discover more precise findings and further insights, the researchers can take the step to conduct a noteworthy study considering the aforesaid variables.

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